

ASSESSMENT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS, ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION IN SPORTS PHYSICAL THERAPIST WHILE TREATING ACUTE INJURY OF ATHLETES

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Abstract

Background: Healthcare professionals, including sports physical therapists, are at high risk for stress, anxiety, and depressive disorders. Sports physical therapists face anxiety while treating acute injuries in athletes and experience job instability, work-life conflict, and various stressors such as workload, interpersonal dynamics, and moral and ethical dilemmas. These factors can interfere with memory, cognitive functions, and clinical performance.

Objective: To assess levels of anxiety, depression, and stress among sports physical therapists treating acute injuries in athletes.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted with a sample size of 63 sports physical therapists selected using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. Data were collected using the DASS-21 questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 25.

Results: The results revealed that male physical therapists exhibited higher rates of depression compared to female physical therapists ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, male physical therapists demonstrated greater levels of anxiety than their female counterparts ($p < 0.001$). However, stress was experienced equally by both male and female physical therapists ($p > 0.075$).

Conclusion: The study concludes that male physical therapists experience significantly higher levels of anxiety and depression compared to female physical therapists, while both genders experience similar levels of stress when treating athletes with severe injuries

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety, depression, and stress are significant challenges for psychologists, psychiatrists, and behavioral scientists worldwide. Among these, depression is recognized by the World Health

Organization as a prevalent mental health disorder. It is characterized by symptoms such as persistent low mood, a lack of interest in activities, feelings of guilt or worthlessness, difficulties with sleep and appetite,

low energy levels, and challenges in maintaining concentration. Anxiety and depression are among the most commonly diagnosed mental health conditions, affecting approximately 10–20% of the population. Stress, a normal part of life, is also a prevalent concern in contemporary societies. A study highlights that 42.28% of physical therapists experience depression, 56.2% suffer from anxiety, and 17.97% report significant levels of stress (1).

Physiotherapists generally have a positive perception of addressing anxiety and depression in patients. However, many acknowledge that they lack the necessary skills to effectively utilize psychosocial interventions (2). Studies also indicate gender-specific differences in injury rates, with women being more susceptible to anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries, concussions, and ankle sprains (3).

For healthcare professionals, managing workplace stress is critical, as high stress levels can negatively affect both their health and their capacity for creative problem-solving (4). Workplace stress and its severity have been directly linked to burnout, a condition characterized by emotional exhaustion, detachment, and diminished personal accomplishment (5). In sports, the majority of injuries sustained by high school athletes tend to be acute, with football being particularly associated with a higher frequency of injuries (6).

Healthcare professionals, including physical therapists, are prone to burnout due to heavy workloads, which often involve providing comprehensive care, ensuring patient safety, and staying updated with knowledge about diseases and treatments. These demands, combined with the emotional toll of interacting with patients experiencing pain or disabilities, can lead to emotional withdrawal and avoidance of close relationships with patients (7). Burnout not only impacts healthcare providers but also compromises the quality of care provided to patients (8).

Among physical therapists, burnout manifests as overwhelming exhaustion, reduced professional efficacy, and increased cynicism, which hinder effective patient engagement (9). Emotional exhaustion, in particular, is an early sign of burnout and a strong predictor of intentions to leave the profession (10).

Sports injuries, which can significantly affect athletes' performance and financial stability, remain a pressing concern. These injuries also result in missed practices and competitions. The frequency of sports injuries varies by type, with joint injuries accounting for 5–6%, tendinopathies for 10–50%, and muscle injuries for 20–60% (11). While sports physiotherapists aim to incorporate psychological techniques in rehabilitation, they often face challenges due to limited confidence and insufficient knowledge of psychological strategies. Previous reviews have noted these barriers but did not specifically address sports physiotherapists or their role in treating athletes (12). The current research aims to evaluate the stress, anxiety, and depression levels experienced by sports physiotherapists while managing athletes with acute injuries. Unlike earlier studies that primarily focused on athletes' mental health and the role of physiotherapists in addressing it, this study emphasizes the mental health of physiotherapists themselves during the treatment process.

HYPOTHESIS

NULL HYPOTHESIS

There is no difference in depression, anxiety and stress among male and female physical therapists while managing acute injury of athletes.

ALTERNATIVE HYPOTHESIS

There is difference in depression, anxiety and stress among male and female physical therapists while managing acute injury of athletes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted to assess the levels of stress, anxiety, and depression among physical therapists while treating athletes with acute injuries. The research spanned a minimum of six months for completion. Both male and female physiotherapists were included in the study (1). Participants consisted of sports physiotherapists aged 25 to 45 years (2), with legal licensure to practice as physiotherapists (2).

Exclusion criteria included physiotherapists who had previously experienced stress, anxiety, or depression (1), those who had not managed acute injuries in over a year, and those currently not in practice. The sample size of 63 participants was calculated using the

Cochrane formula (3). A non-probability convenience sampling method was employed to recruit participants from sports academies, clubs, and clinics in Pakistan. Prior to data collection, participants were provided with an informed consent form. The data collection process was designed to respect and consider cultural and religious sensitivities. The Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21) was utilized as the outcome measurement tool to evaluate the mental health parameters. Data analysis was performed using SPSS-25, with percentage, mean, and standard deviation used to present demographic and non-categorical data.

A t-test was conducted to examine the significance of variables. The level of significance for depression was

set at $p = 0.001$, for anxiety at $p = 0.002$, and for stress at $p = 0.75$.

RESULTS

The results revealed that male physical therapists exhibited higher rates of depression compared to female physical therapists ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, male physical therapists demonstrated greater levels of anxiety than their female counterparts ($p < 0.001$). However, stress was experienced equally by both male and female physical therapists ($p > 0.075$). The study concludes that male physical therapists experience significantly higher levels of anxiety and depression compared to female physical therapists, while both genders experience similar levels of stress when treating athletes with severe injuries.

Table 1: Description of Depression Subscale (DASS-21)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Normal	19	30.2
Mild	7	11.1
Moderate	20	31.7
Severe	17	27.0
Total	63	100.0

The responses to the Depression subscale (DASS-21) are displayed in the table above. The greatest percentage of individuals, or 20 out of 63 experienced moderate depression, followed by normal depression (19), severe depression (17), and mild depression (7).

Table 2: Description of Anxiety Subscale (DASS-21)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Normal	14	22.2
Mild	4	6.3
Moderate	11	17.5
Severe	16	25.4
Extremely Severe	18	28.6
Total	63	100.0

The Anxiety Subscale (DASS-21) responses shown in the table above of the 63 physical therapists, 18 had extremely severe anxiety, 16 had severe anxiety, 11 had moderate anxiety, 4 had mild anxiety, and 14 had no anxiety at all.

Table 3: Description of Stress Subscale (DASS-21)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Normal	29	46.0
Mild	15	23.8
Moderate	19	30.2
Severe	0	0.00

Extremely Severe	0	0.00
Total	63	100.0

The answers to the DASS-21 stress subscale are displayed above. 29 out of the 63 physical therapists reported no stress, 19 reported a moderate amount of stress, and 15 reported a mild level of stress.

Table 4: Description of t test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Depression Subscale (DASS-21)	15.282	.000	4.491	61	.000	1.20105	.26746	.66622	1.73588
Equal variance assumed									
Equal variance not assumed			5.015	59.682	.000	1.20105	.23948	.72197	1.68013
Anxiety Subscale (DASS-21)	15.436	.000	3.316	61	.002	1.19789	.36121	.47562	1.92017
Equal variance assumed									
Equal variance not assumed			3.625	60.960	.001	1.19789	.33046	.53709	1.85870
Stress Subscale (DASS-21)	1.680	.200	1.809	61	.075	.39579	.21884	-.04180	.83338
Equal variance assumed									
Equal variance not assumed			1.836	54.081	.072	.39579	.21556	-.03636	.82794

The table showed that there is a significant difference in depression level of male and female physical therapists ($p > 0.001$), the significant difference in anxiety level of male and female physical therapists ($p > 0.001$) and there is no significant difference in stress level of male and female physical therapists ($p < 0.075$).

DISCUSSION

This study assesses the levels of stress, anxiety, and depression experienced by male and female physical therapists who treat athletes with acute injuries. The sample consisted of 63 physical therapists with an average age of 30.33 years. According to the study's findings the degree of depression in men and women differs significantly. physical therapists ($p > 0.001$), in the considerable variation between male and female anxiety levels physical therapists ($p > 0.001$) and stress levels of men and women do not differ substantially from each other physical therapists ($p < 0.075$).

Pamela K Schraedley M.A et al. studied disparities between genders in the correlates of teenage depression symptoms. It was discovered that

depression symptoms varied by gender. Depression affects about twice as many women as it does men. This study shows contrast to our research (1).

Shuai Liu et al studied gender disparities in mental health issues among medical professionals during the COVID-19 pandemic. When compared to male HCWs, female HCWs scored significantly higher on anxiety, stress, and depression. Additionally, female HCWs reported a higher prevalence in each of these categories than did male HCWs. Mental health problems(2)

In 2022, Abeer Hamza and his colleagues did a study on how COVID-19 affects depression and anxiety among Saudi Arabian physical therapists. 74 (63%) and 65 (55.5%) of the 117 physical therapists who finished the study and took part in it reported having symptoms of anxiety and depression, respectively. This study concurred with our findings (3).

Hebatallah Mohamad Aly et al, assessed Egyptian healthcare professionals (physicians, dentists, pharmacists, physiotherapists, nurses, technicians and administrators). The findings indicated that 98.5% of them reported moderate to severe stress, while just

1.3% reported low perceived stress. Ninety-five percent of the participants reported having some degree of anxiety, with mild anxiety accounting for the largest percentage at around forty percent, moderate anxiety at about thirty-two percent, and severe anxiety at eighteen percent. Five percent of the individuals reported having no generalized anxiety. 94% of subjects reported having mild to severe depression. The result shows contrast to our research.(4).

Dr. Shailesh Parmar and Dr. Hemal Patel compare the health-related quality of life and stress experienced by academic and hospital physiotherapists. 84.31% of the clinical therapists said they were under moderate stress, and 7.84% said they were under high stress. Conversely, only 3.92% of non-clinical therapists reported high stress levels, while 78.43% reported moderate stress. These results imply that, in comparison to their non-clinical counterparts, a greater proportion of clinical therapists endure moderate to high levels of stress. This study showed contrast with our research (5).

B Shivananda Nayak et al. assess The Bahamas healthcare practitioners' pandemic caused by COVID-19 depression, anxiety, and stress. In this study, 42.28% of 395 HCWs had light 56.2% of respondents reported mild to severe anxiety symptoms, 17.97% reported mild to severe stress symptoms, and 56.2% reported mild to severe depression symptoms. This study showed contrast with our research(6).

CONCLUSION

The study results concluded that anxiety and depression are considerably more common in male

physical therapists than in female physical therapists while stress is experienced by both male and female physical therapists equally while treating athletes with acute injuries.

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APPENDIX-III:Questionnaire

DASS21	Name:	Date:
<p>Please read each statement and circle a number 0, 1, 2 or 3 which indicates how much the statement applied to you <i>over the past week</i>. There are no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any statement.</p> <p><i>The rating scale is as follows:</i></p> <p>0 Did not apply to me at all 1 Applied to me to some degree, or some of the time 2 Applied to me to a considerable degree, or a good part of time 3 Applied to me very much, or most of the time</p>		
1 I found it hard to wind down	0	1 2 3
2 I was aware of dryness of my mouth	0	1 2 3
3 I couldn't seem to experience any positive feeling at all	0	1 2 3
4 I experienced breathing difficulty (eg, excessively rapid breathing, breathlessness in the absence of physical exertion)	0	1 2 3
5 I found it difficult to work up the initiative to do things	0	1 2 3
6 I tended to over-react to situations	0	1 2 3
7 I experienced trembling (eg, in the hands)	0	1 2 3
8 I felt that I was using a lot of nervous energy	0	1 2 3
9 I was worried about situations in which I might panic and make a fool of myself	0	1 2 3
10 I felt that I had nothing to look forward to	0	1 2 3
11 I found myself getting agitated	0	1 2 3
12 I found it difficult to relax	0	1 2 3
13 I felt down-hearted and blue	0	1 2 3
14 I was intolerant of anything that kept me from getting on with what I was doing	0	1 2 3
15 I felt I was close to panic	0	1 2 3
16 I was unable to become enthusiastic about anything	0	1 2 3
17 I felt I wasn't worth much as a person	0	1 2 3
18 I felt that I was rather touchy	0	1 2 3
19 I was aware of the action of my heart in the absence of physical exertion (eg, sense of heart rate increase, heart missing a beat)	0	1 2 3
20 I felt scared without any good reason	0	1 2 3
21 I felt that life was meaningless	0	1 2 3

DASS-21 Scoring Instructions

The DASS-21 should not be used to replace a face to face clinical interview. If you are experiencing significant emotional difficulties you should contact your GP for a referral to a qualified professional.

Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale - 21 Items (DASS-21)

The Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale - 21 Items (DASS-21) is a set of three self-report scales designed to measure the emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress.

Each of the three DASS-21 scales contains 7 items, divided into subscales with similar content. The depression scale assesses dysphoria, hopelessness, devaluation of life, self-deprecation, lack of interest / involvement, anhedonia and inertia. The anxiety scale assesses autonomic arousal, skeletal muscle effects, situational anxiety, and subjective experience of anxious affect. The stress scale is sensitive to levels of chronic non-specific arousal. It assesses difficulty relaxing, nervous arousal, and being easily upset / agitated, irritable / over-reactive and impatient. Scores for depression, anxiety and stress are calculated by summing the scores for the relevant items.

The DASS-21 is based on a dimensional rather than a categorical conception of psychological disorder. The assumption on which the DASS-21 development was based (and which was confirmed by the research data) is that the differences between the depression, anxiety and the stress experienced by normal subjects and clinical populations are essentially differences of degree. The DASS-21 therefore has no direct implications for the allocation of patients to discrete diagnostic categories postulated in classificatory systems such as the DSM and ICD.

Recommended cut-off scores for conventional severity labels (normal, moderate, severe) are as follows:

NB Scores on the DASS-21 will need to be multiplied by 2 to calculate the final score.

	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
Normal	0-9	0-7	0-14
Mild	10-13	8-9	15-18
Moderate	14-20	10-14	19-25
Severe	21-27	15-19	26-33
Extremely Severe	28+	20+	34+

Lovibond, S.H. & Lovibond, P.F. (1995). Manual for the Depression Anxiety & Stress Scales. (2nd Ed.)Sydney: Psychology Foundation.